

LESSON LEARNT IN HEI TEACHING AFTER THE CORONAVIRUS PANDEMIC: THE SOULSS PROJECT

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Abstract. As lockdowns ease and students return to campuses across Europe, it is becoming increasingly clear that the higher education landscape has shifted dramatically. HEIs provide flexible blends of synchronous, asynchronous, and face-to-face (f2f) instruction, enabling tertiary-level teachers and students to switch seamlessly between delivery options. It is crucial in the actual post-emergency situation to support teachers who need the training to design optimal combinations of different delivery modes that utilize the unique strengths and overcome the potential constraints of each method. Among the lessons learned from the emergency, the Universal Learning Design (UDL) principles are among the most important. The Erasmus+ project Scaffolding Online University Learning: Support Systems (SOULSS) envisages supporting teachers in implementing UDL in their teaching, considering new technologies and approaches.

Keywords: Universal Design of Learning - UDL, Inclusive higher Education Systems, Supporting Digital Capabilities, Stimulating Innovative Learning and Teaching Practices.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most critical aspects of the recent Coronavirus pandemic was its global impact in all the world. It was especially true in the formal aspects of citizens' life: governments worldwide adopted several strategies whose application was meaningful and general regarding public offices, especially public universities. The suspension of face-to-face lessons in higher education institutions was generalized worldwide and generally accepted by public opinion. It was different for primary education. In several countries, at least kindergartens stayed open, and most elementary schools followed after the first period of forced online education. The difference in the approach resulted from most political leaders and decision-makers thinking that adult people could easily switch to online learning. Some teachers considered this situation as an excellent opportunity to test online education in all subjects and involving a massive number of students (Sepulveda-Escobar & Morrison, 2020), while another part felt worried in front of this unexpected task that added stress factors to their situations (Ozamiz-Etxebarria et al., 2021). The latter study is a review, and it is interesting to underline as the results generally cover university teachers from all continents. Institutions worldwide tried to support professors in promoting the acquisition and application of new pedagogical approaches and technical skills, like the case of Brazil

(Gusso et al., 2020). However, each professor reacted differently depending on their attitude and experience (Teng & Wu, 2021; Alqabbani et al., 2021).

Generally speaking, it was not an error to consider higher education as an environment more ready to accept online learning than secondary and primary education. University professors could apply effective instructional strategies to guarantee course continuity (Mahmood, 2021), while primary school teachers could only do the same sometimes, primarily because of the difference in readiness of students and families to adapt to the new rules and educational ecosystems. For example, studies show that the passage from face-to-face to online was very punitive for students with disabilities in primary education (Montanari et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2022). Instead, university students' attitude toward e-learning was more positive because of the involved persons' maturity and capacity to have a peer-to-peer relationship with their instructors (Tejedor, 2020). Also, university professors were, in general, more ready to accept the new ecosystem in comparison to their colleagues from primary and secondary schools due to the different kinds of relations needed in class, so including blended courses in the future in university curricula has been suggested as a good option (Giovannella & Passarelli, 2020).

The future of university teaching is at a critical point: the pandemic emergency seems to be disappearing, but nobody knows the near future. The impact of the emergency has been huge on a teaching approach (Ojo & Lorenzini, 2021) but also in terms of psychological effects on professors themselves (Akour et al., 2020). The starting Erasmus+ Project Scaffolding Online University Learning: Support Systems (SOULSS) aims to contribute to the definition of a better strategy to scaffold university professors and students in their activities, focusing on one of the most valuable pedagogical framework in this field: the Universal Design of Learning (UDL).

2. THE UDL LEGACY

The universal design movement inspired the Universal Design for Learning concepts in architecture and product development, initially formulated by Ronald L. Mace at North Carolina State University. According to the Center for Universal Design (CUD), UD is "the design of products and environments to be usable by all people, to the greatest extent possible, without the need for adaptation or specialized design." (Connell et al., 1997).

This definition can be modified. For example, to apply UD to teaching and learning activities, this basic definition can be modified to "the design of teaching and learning products and environments to be usable by all people, to the greatest extent possible, without the need for adaptation or specialized design."

Product developers, architects, and engineers at CUD established seven UD principles to consider in the design of any product or environment (Connell et al., 1997, cit in. Crow, 2007):

- Equitable Use,
- Flexibility in Use,
- Simple and Intuitive Use,
- Perceptible Information,

- Tolerance for Error,
- Low Physical Effort,
- Size and Space for Approach and Use.

Planning a lesson using the UDL framework is a process that requires a clear definition of four fundamental components: Goals; Assessments; Methods; Materials (Meyer et al., 2014). The UDL Cycle of instructional planning can be summarized in figure 1:

Figure 1. UDL Cycle of instructional planning (based on Rao & Meo, 2016)

UDL principles were previously examined and implemented by some project partners during the Erasmus+ project SUCCESS4ALL for primary and secondary schools focused on online support for students with special educational needs. The scope of this project, which ended at the beginning of 2023, was to provide guidelines and a self-paced online course based on Universal Design for Learning principles as well as an e-learning platform and a networking center that could support the work of teachers and caregivers whenever needed. During the project, a course dedicated to UDL was created to help school teachers implement the UDL principles in inclusive education. This course is available online at the SUCCESS4ALL homepage (SUCCESS UDL Course).

3. THE SOULSS PROJECT

The Erasmus+ Project SOULSS aims to help the diffusion of the UDL approach in the HEIs by creating and supporting dedicated digital self-paced learning courses. The project

intends to support higher education institutions in their digital transformation. During the last decades, several institutions created online learning material and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs), but their impact on the general public could have been more substantial. The outbreak of the COVID-19 crisis forced all higher education institutions (HEIs) to adopt online teaching on a scale never seen before. Now, as countries across Europe start to ease lockdown restrictions and prepare for 'the day after the pandemic,' three dramatic shifts in the higher education landscape can be seen:

Many students may now prefer the increased flexibility the blend of delivery options offers.

HEIs who started offering online courses when the pandemic began will continue to offer them to reach different student populations who cannot attend studies on campus.

The continued threat of other health-related crises and restrictions will require HEIs to increase their institutional resilience by enabling teachers and students to switch seamlessly between delivery options.

As a result of these shifts in the post-pandemic higher education landscape, many HEIs will now expect their educators to be able to design and deliver a range of flexible hybrid teaching and learning options. These new expectations will require educators to be able to 'think like an expert instructional designer,' adapt their pedagogy and re-design optimal blends of delivery options that support effective and inclusive instruction for all their students. Unless this training gap is filled, we assume that teachers who lack the additional expertise, skills, and attitudes to meet these new expectations will:

Tend to replicate their F2F courses instead of re-designing them to overcome the potential barriers and utilize the relative strengths of different delivery modes.

Directly affect the extent to which each student is included or remains excluded from developing their full learning potential.

Based on these assumptions, the SOULSS project will develop, pilot, and evaluate the impact of a training course to build teachers' capacity to design:

- inclusive UDL-based instruction,
- small interventions to keep on track at-risk students identified by an early warning system,
- optimal combinations of hybrid learning environments that utilize the strengths of different delivery modes.

Educational decision-makers represent the target group at different levels, such as policymakers, educational institutions, and teachers from different European countries. Moreover, all Higher Education stakeholders have been involved: students, teachers, and university staff. Students are the main target group of the project, an essential aspect of tertiary education nowadays.

More specifically, the project will implement a learning platform open for all HEIs with three newly created online MOOC-like learning units to provide them with a stable digital environment. The units will follow three paths:

- Innovative Technologies to gather feedback in Online Education,
- Innovative approach for Online Teaching,
- Universal Design of Learning.

In the first two years of the project life, partners will design and implement the platform and the learning units, while the last (third) year will be dedicated to testing activities in all HEIs involved in the project in several European countries such as Italy, Spain, Portugal, Greece, and Lithuania.

4. CONCLUSIONS

During the last pandemic, Universities had to switch to flexible pedagogical models based primarily on online learning. UDL is the key to this approach as it provides a concrete framework for creating immersive courses, even for special education. The Erasmus+ project SOULSS aims to take advantage of this framework and from the experience that project partners have obtained from another European project focused on special education and the usage of UDL. SOULSS case is different as it is focused on tertiary education. The SOULSS project partnership believes UDL principles alongside solid evaluation mechanisms can help achieve the goal of disseminating innovative technologies and methods in the field of Higher Education.

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